

Milestone

Optimisation of feed formulations, feed trials, FCR, fish physiological status, gut integrity, and product quality

DATE: 31/10/25

DELIVERABLE NUMBER: Milestone 4

General Information

Call identifier: HORIZON-CL6-2022-FARM2FORK-01-05
 GA Number: 101084549
 Start date of project: 01/11/2022
 Work Package: WP4
 Task: Task 1-4
 Type: Deliverable
 Number: M4 Optimisation of feed formulations, feed trials, FCR, fish physiological status, gut integrity, and product quality
 Version: 1
 Due Date: End of Month 36 – 31 October 2025
 Submission date: 31 October 2025
 Responsible organisation(s): **GALWAY**, CIIMAR, KW, ZUT, ICR
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Document Type		
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DEL	Technical reports identified as deliverables in the Description of Work	
MoM	Minutes of Meeting	
MAN	Procedures and user manuals	X
WOR	Working document, issued as preparatory documents to a Technical report	
INF	Information and Notes	

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
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Table of Contents

Table of Contents.....	3
Executive Summary	4
1. Introduction.....	5
1.1. Background on the feed development	5
1.2. Feed Formulation Optimisation.....	5
1.3. Aquafeed 3.0- Circular feeds	5
2. Commercially important Freshwater farmed fish species in Europe.....	6
2.1. Salmonids- Atlantic salmon and rainbow trout	6
2.2. Cyprinid-common carp.....	8
2.3. Percids- European perch	10
3. Methodology in assessing novel circular feed ingredients	11
3.1. Integration of circular feed ingredients into commercial diet formulation.....	11
3.2. Growth and feed utilisation assessment	13
3.3. Research ethical standards, data, and sample collection	14
3.4. Blood sampling	15
3.4.1. Blood cell parameters.....	15
3.4.2. Biochemical parameters	15
3.4.3. Immune parameters	15
3.5 Nutritional histomorphological assessment	17
3.6 Gut integrity and molecular microbiome profiling	18
3.7 Gene expression	18
3.8. Consumer product quality evaluation	19
3.9. Data analysis and performance assessment.....	21
3.10. Economic optimisation	22
4. Integrating environmental impact in the circular feed assessment	22
5. Conclusion.....	24
References	26

Executive Summary

SAFE aims to evaluate the use of circularly sourced feed macro ingredients to optimise fish feed formulations and assess their impact on the growth and physiological performance indicators of key freshwater fish species, specifically Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*), rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*), European perch (*Perca fluviatilis*), and Common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*), along with their carcass quality. The circular feed initiative emphasises upcycling aquaculture waste streams and processing by-products into high-quality fish feed materials, forging a circular, sustainable nutrient loop. This is intended to reduce feed costs, optimise formulations, manage aquaculture waste effectively, and enhance fish yield. This document outlines the systematic assessment of circular feed macro-ingredient production, including an analysis of feed nutrient quality and an investigation into circular feed utilisation across salmon, perch, carp, and trout aquaculture. This work also evaluates the consequent health performances in fish species models and assesses the organoleptic properties of the resulting fish carcass. Fish sludge from aquaculture effluent is used to cultivate worms and eukaryotic organisms, such as microalgae and mushrooms, to generate substantial, low-cost, high-quality proteins for fish feed formulations. For empirical validation, commercially sourced fish models are acclimated to ex situ conditions within the culture facility and maintained in accordance with the EU Directive 2010/63/EU. During an 8 to 12-week feeding trial, the feed formulations are administered to the experimental fish groups using a dose-response design to observe performance across different inclusion rates. The impact of the test feeds on the fish models is rigorously assessed by measuring critical performance indicators, namely: growth performance, morphometrics, nutrient utilisation, and apparent digestibility; haematological parameter measurement specifically, blood cell counts, red cell indices to assess gaseous exchange and immune status; biochemical parameter evaluation including metabolite levels and antioxidant enzymes activity as stress biomarkers; gene expressions analysis to assess gene regulation influencing physiological and immune responses; histo-architectural assessments of fish liver and intestine to provide insights into feed absorption and digestibility; and carcass assessment to evaluate fillet quality and hedonic acceptance. Gut microbiome assessment measures gut microbial composition and structural balance. SAFE biodata evaluation provides the performance benchmark to validate recommendations for the successful mainstreaming of the circular feed model into commercial aquaculture practices.

1. Introduction

1.1. Background on the feed development

Fish farming is a sustainable food source that aims to address the growing protein deficit in human nutrition. With global demand for protein steadily increasing, aquaculture offers an efficient and sustainable approach to meeting this essential need. Cultivating fish in controlled environments entails providing targeted nutrition through specially formulated feeds. Fish production in aquaculture relies heavily on the provision of artificial food to enhance fish welfare and increase yields (Toni et al., 2019). The effectiveness of this approach is significantly influenced by the nutrient profile of the feed consumed, among other contributing factors (Ribeiro et al., 2019). A well-balanced diet, rich in essential nutrients, typically includes protein (balanced amino acids), carbohydrates, energy (primarily from lipids), and micronutrients (vitamins, bioactive compounds, prebiotics, enzymes, probiotics, and minerals). This combination is crucial for normal growth, health, and overall performance in fish. Factors such as ingredient quality, formulation techniques, and the specific dietary needs of different fish species all play essential roles in determining the success of feed formulation and aquaculture production. Aquaculture nutritionists must implement effective feed formulation strategies to maximise nutrient absorption and digestibility, thereby delivering the highest feed-to-protein conversion ratio.

1.2. Feed Formulation Optimisation

Feed optimisation is fundamental in the field of fish nutrition research, as it significantly affects growth, health, and overall production efficiency. Optimising feed involves designing diets that align with the specific nutritional needs of the farmed fish species while taking into account their life stages, ecotypes, culturing system used (e.g., recirculating aquaculture systems, open cage, raceways) and environmental conditions (e.g., warmer water culture, colder temperate waters). This tailored approach guarantees that fish receive the essential nutrients needed for optimal growth and well-being, ultimately leading to increased productivity in aquaculture. However, the choice of feedstuffs and their associated economic costs are crucial factors during feed formulation. For instance, protein-based ingredients, such as fishmeal, are among the most expensive components of aquafeed (Nunes et al., 2022). Given the high demand and cost of fishmeal, coupled with socioeconomic and environmental pressures, the aquaculture industry is actively seeking more affordable and sustainable alternative protein sources. While the search for alternative proteins has led to the exploration of options such as plant proteins, animal by-products, insect meals, and single-cell proteins, concerns have been raised about their nutritional safety, sustainability, and environmental footprints (Sondergaard et al., 2023; Ileancho et al., 2025a). More innovative feed formulation strategies that emphasise circular economy principles can strengthen the aquafeed industry.

1.3 Aquafeed 3.0- Circular feeds

The aquafeed industry is currently undergoing a remarkable transformation, marked by a deepening commitment to innovative feed production technologies that are both profitable and environmentally friendly. One of the most recent developments in this field is the circular feed (CF) concept, also known as Aquafeed 3.0, an approach that promises to redefine feed production techniques in aquaculture (Colombo et al., 2023). This approach emphasises the principles of sustainability and resource efficiency, focusing on the recycling of nutrients (nitrogen and phosphorus) and waste materials to create a more closed-loop system in aquaculture (European Commission, 2021; Masi et al., 2025). In practice, CF promotes the recovery of nutrients from aquaculture effluent to produce protein biomass (Colombo et al., 2023; Petterson et al., 2025). Moreover, this innovation emphasises nutritional quality, resource efficiency, and nutrient recapture to develop novel protein sources for sustainable aquafeed production. Formulations derived from circular feed practices can be enriched with micro-ingredients needed for optimal fish growth and health. The circular feed concept also aligns with the growing demand for environmentally friendly practices in the aquaculture industry (Verreth et al., 2023), whereas promoting the 3R (replace, reduce, recycle) concept delivers waste reduction, lowering feed cost (by replacing expensive conventional feed ingredients with less

costly alternatives), reducing energy expenditure through sustainable practices, which not only benefits ecosystems but also enhances the economic viability of aquaculture operations (Chary et al., 2024; Kurniawan et al., 2025; Petterson et al., 2025). As the industry faces increasing scrutiny regarding its environmental footprint (Zhang et al., 2024), implementing circular feed solutions presents a proactive approach to addressing these challenges.

2. Commercially important Freshwater farmed fish species in Europe

2.1. Salmonids- Atlantic salmon and rainbow trout

Salmonids are a widely distributed and ecologically important group of temperate fish, critical for both food webs and nutrient cycling (Foote et al., 2025). Salmonids, including Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*) and rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*), are important species in commercial fisheries and have been increasingly integrated into global aquaculture, especially in Europe (Brand et al., 2024). This shift has significantly contributed to protein sources for both human consumption and livestock nutrition, underscoring their role in ensuring food security. Salmonids represent a significant group in aquaculture, with around 75% of their global production derived from aquaculture practices (Pandey et al., 2023; Budhathoki et al., 2025). By 2019, Atlantic salmon dominated this sector, comprising approximately 70% of farmed salmonids globally. Following closely was rainbow trout, which accounted for about 24% of the total farmed salmonid production (Ziegler et al., 2023). Between 1984 and 2022, farmed salmonid production increased from 227,990 tonnes to approximately 4.2 million tonnes (FAO, 2024; Budhathoki et al., 2025). This substantial increase in production has led to a rise in value, surging from USD\$784.06 million to USD\$29.81 billion (Budhathoki et al., 2025). The aquaculture production of salmonids has experienced significant enhancement over recent years, primarily due to advancements in production technologies, the development of hatcheries, and improvements in feed formulation strategies. These factors have not only increased the efficiency of salmon farming but have also contributed to a rise in the market value of these fish (Refstie and Åsgård, 2009). The consumption of salmonids (particularly salmon) has surged in popularity due to their excellent nutritional profile, particularly their high levels of omega-3 and omega-6 fatty acids (Rodrigues et al., 2024; Lámfalusy et al., 2025). Importantly, salmonids are a well-established model species for nutritional assessments and feed validation trials. Rainbow trout are widely used as a model species in early-stage experiments due to their shorter production cycle, tolerance to varied rearing conditions, and lower testing costs. Trials with trout typically focus on growth performance, digestibility, palatability, and effects on flesh quality, while also monitoring stress tolerance and immune responses. Atlantic salmon, by contrast, are the primary commercial species in global salmonid aquaculture, and feed trials are generally larger-scale and longer-term, often conducted in recirculating aquaculture systems or sea cages (Figure 1).

Figure 1: A) The natural lifecycle of Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*, Willoughby, 2009), B) Commercial salmon production lifecycle (FAO, 2009).

Salmonids (e.g., salmon and trout) are carnivorous species with high protein and energy requirements necessary for adequate growth and metabolic function (Kaushik and Medale, 1994; Villasante et al., 2019). Their diet must typically contain 40–50% crude protein and an appropriate amino acid balance to ensure optimal growth and systemic physiological support (Table 1). However, this protein requirement can vary depending on factors such as the fish's life stage, water temperature, and other environmental conditions (FAO, 2019). These variables can influence their nutritional needs and affect their growth performance. Traditional fishmeal has been a primary protein source in their feed, but the increasing demand for sustainable aquaculture has highlighted the need for alternative protein sources. These alternative ingredients must provide a high-quality protein profile that matches the nutritional value of fishmeal (Hardy, 1996). Alternative feed ingredients, including plant-based proteins, insect meal, algal meal, local marine ingredients, and animal by-products, have been explored in several studies as substitutes for fishmeal and fish oil in salmonid diets (Hardy, 1996; Simon et al., 2025). These alternatives aim to reduce dependence on marine products while enhancing environmental sustainability (Boissy et al., 2011; McGrath et al., 2015). While these options demonstrate considerable potential, their production processes pose notable environmental challenges (Wind et al., 2022;

Budhathoki et al., 2025). Therefore, it is crucial to pursue further technological advancements and scale these alternatives effectively to maximise their benefits and ensure a more sustainable aquaculture industry.

Table 1: Typical environmental conditions required in commercially important European farmed fish species and feed class sizes.

Common name	Rainbow trout	Atlantic salmon	Common carp	European perch
Species	<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>	<i>Salmo salar</i>	<i>Cyprinus carpio</i>	<i>Perca fluviatilis</i>
Optimal temperature (°C)	12-19	16-18	20-25	18-28
Suboptimal temperature(°C)	> 21	> 23	> 30	<16/>21
pH	6.5-8.5	6.5-8.5	6.5-9.0	7-7.5
Feed size (mm)				
Early fry	<0.44	0.3	0.5-1.0	< 0.5
Fry	0.44-0.59	0.5	1.0-1.3	0.5-0.8
Fingerling	1.5-2.0	> 0.8-1.8	0.5-3	0.8-1.2
Grower	2.0-5.0	2.0-5.0	0.5-5	2-3
Broodstock	5.0	7.0-9.0	5.0	4-6
Reference	FAO (2009)	Lall, 2009; Wade et al.(2019)	FAO (2009)	Takác et al.2024; CABI (2019)

NRC (1993)

A circular feed usage strategy can offer an alternative technological solution in aquaculture, with the potential to significantly optimise feed formulation for salmonid production. The circular usage principle emphasises the recovery, recycling, and reuse of aquaculture waste and by-products to develop valuable nutrient resources for fish feed (Masi et al., 2025). The generation of fish sludge from salmon farms poses a substantial management challenge, particularly since as much as 50% of it results from feed spillage (uneaten feed) (Sele et al., 2024; Malzahn et al., 2023). However, this byproduct is rich in valuable nutrients, including protein, lipid (including polyunsaturated fatty acids), and minerals (Liland et al., 2023; Sele et al., 2024). The Norwegian salmon industry alone generates an estimated 500,000 tonnes (dry matter) of sludge annually, with the largest volumes recoverable from grow-out net-pens at sea (Aas and Åsgard, 2017). Fish sludge is converted into nutrient biomass for fish feed, providing a sustainable solution for waste management in aquaculture. Specifically, the sludge can be used to cultivate insect larvae and polychaetes (worms), consequently generating protein biomass that establishes a circular feed model, and recaptures lost nutrients. (Liland et al., 2023; Malzahn et al., 2023). A previous study by Ytrestoyl et al. (2016) highlights the significant nutrient recovery potential of fish sludge, reporting yields (per 100 g dry weight) of up to 32.9% crude protein, 14% lipid, 22.1% ash, and 19.2% energy. Realising the full potential of a circular use model to enhance salmonid aquaculture may require a detailed assessment of its efficacy in improving species growth and health, along with the establishment of a safety and regulatory policy framework for its mainstreaming in commercial aquaculture.

2.2. Cyprinid-common carp

The common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) is one of the oldest domesticated and most widely farmed freshwater fish species worldwide, serving as a cornerstone of inland aquaculture. Domesticated initially in Asia and later disseminated across Europe by the Romans and by monastic fish-culture traditions, the species has been selectively bred for enhanced growth, adaptability, and resilience (FAO, 2009). Global aquaculture production of common carp currently exceeds 4 million tonnes annually, corresponding to nearly 10% of total global finfish aquaculture output (FAO, 2025). In Europe, carp farming is predominantly concentrated in Central and Eastern regions, particularly in Poland, Czechia, and Hungary, where it sustains traditional earthen pond-based polyculture or monoculture systems that contribute not only to food security but also to ecosystem services such as nutrient recycling, biodiversity conservation, and water purification (FAO,

2021; Woynarovich et al., 2010). The species exhibits remarkable environmental tolerance, thriving at temperatures of 20–25 °C and pH levels of 6.5–9.0 (FAO, 2009). Common carp are omnivorous, feeding on natural pond biota (benthos, zooplankton, detritus, and macrophytes) and a variety of supplementary feeds, including cereals (e.g. wheat, triticale, rye) and formulated diets. Their dietary protein requirement typically ranges from 28–38% depending on the life stage and production intensity (NRC, 1993; Eljasik et al., 2022). Traditionally farmed following the Dubisch method (3-year cycle), which represents the classical semi-intensive culture system for common carp, developed in Central Europe. It is based on a three-pond sequence: spawning or nursery, fingerling (rearing), and grow-out ponds, each designed to meet the species biological needs during successive life stages (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Extensive production of common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*, FAO 2009).

Broodstock are placed in shallow, vegetated spawning ponds in late spring when the water temperature reaches around 18–22 °C, where natural spawning occurs. After hatching, larvae feed on plankton and benthic organisms, and once they reach a few centimetres in length, they are transferred to rearing ponds at high density for further growth. Supplementary feeding with cereals complements the natural food base, accelerating development to fingerling size (FAO 2009, Woynarovich et al., 2010). Fingerlings are then graded and stocked into grow-out ponds at lower densities, where they are cultured for two growing seasons until reaching the market size of 1–1.5 kg. The Dubisch system relies primarily on natural pond productivity, supported by fertilisation and careful water management, rather than on intensive feed inputs. Its ecological

efficiency is enhanced through nutrient recycling and biological self-purification, which maintain good water quality (FAO 2009, Woynarovich et al., 2010). The species' ability to convert low-value organic matter into high-quality animal protein with minimal feed input underscores its continued relevance to sustainable freshwater aquaculture. Common carp thus remains a model species for circular bioeconomy approaches, linking traditional pond aquaculture heritage with modern innovations in feed optimisation and environmental performance (FAO, 2021).

2.3. Percids- European perch

Aquaculture diversification efforts are driving the domestication of promising species for scaled production. This initiative is driven by the need for a more resilient and sustainable global food system, while also reducing the pressure on wild stocks and protecting aquatic ecosystems from degradation. The European perch (*Perca fluviatilis*) is a prime freshwater candidate for aquaculture expansion, given its potential to deliver high-quality, value-added products that can satisfy consumer demand and stimulate market growth. Its potential for both sustainability and profitability makes it an attractive option for aquaculturists seeking to expand their offerings and contribute to the industry's overall development (Overton et al., 2015; Policar et al., 2019). The global annual aquaculture production of European perch has been estimated at around 900 tonnes (FAO, 2021). The perch industry requires significant developmental investment to scale up production and meet current market demand. The percid fish aquaculture sector, valued at approximately €8.5 million with an average market price of over €6 kg⁻¹, shows significant growth potential (FAO 2019). However, as in the broader aquaculture industry, production costs and price competition remain notable challenges, thereby driving research and development efforts to reduce production costs. This is primarily achieved by improving husbandry practices (e.g., growth and survival rates), optimising hatchery development, and enhancing overall production technology, which remains the main bottleneck limiting continued expansion (Policar et al., 2019).

Among other critical factors to consider are understanding the perch's nutritional requirements and optimising feed formulations. European perch is a prominent predator that exhibits size-dependent changes in both its diet and feeding behaviours. The fish species undergo a significant dietary shift as they age. They start by feeding on zooplankton as larvae, then transition to larger invertebrates and fish as juveniles, and finally become predominantly piscivorous as adults (Cicala et al., 2020). Given its carnivorous nature, perch require a diet with a significantly high protein content, typically reported to be between 40% and 62% (FAO, 2019; Brännas and Strand, 2015; Penka et al., 2025), under an optimum temperature regime between 18-28°C (Table 1) (Hokanson, 1977; Takács et al., 2024; Fiogbe and Kestemont, 2003). For emerging aquaculture species such as perch, the central challenge in feed formulation is defining the growth-promoting composition and balancing the ratios of dietary protein, amino acids, lipids, and carbohydrates (Raubenheimer et al., 2012; Brännas and Strand, 2015). Crucially, the feed formulation must also account for the fish's life stage and environmental parameters (temperature) (Kestemont et al., 1996), a necessity driven by the fact that perch still lack a dedicated, standardised feed formula (Kumar et al., 2019; Geay and Kestemont, 2015).

It is necessary to develop a cost-effective, viable nutritional formula for perch farming, primarily because the use of fishmeal, despite being an exceptional protein source, is constrained by economic and environmental factors. The desire for sustainable and cost-efficient perch production has already led researchers to investigate several alternative protein ingredients in prior studies, including wheat gluten (Kamaszewski et al., 2020); processed soybean meal (Kumar et al., 2019); soybean meals (Kasper et al., 2007); partially defatted *Hermetia illucens* larva meal (Stejskal et al., 2020); defatted microalgae meal (*Haematococcus pluvialis*) combined with soy protein isolate (Jiang et al., 2019); mixture cricket meal (*Acheta domesticus*) and superworm meal (*Zophobas morio*) (Tilami et al., 2020). Although their use in the perch diet shows promise, the commercial integration of these alternatives depends on resolving key concerns about their economic cost, life-cycle assessment (LCA) potential, and consistent availability. Future research should investigate protein resources derived from circular aquaculture as a novel, sustainable macroingredient for perch feed formulation. The use of circular processes that leverage the capacity of certain invertebrate species to remediate unprocessed fish sludge shows promising potential (Pettersen et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2019). This approach aligns with the growing interest in including alternative low-trophic organisms such as marine polychaete worms, earthworms,

and gammarids in aquafeeds (Parolini et al., 2020; Pombo et al., 2020). Specifically, species such as the Black Soldier Fly (*Hermetia illucens*) and the marine polychaete (*Hediste diversicolor*) can valorise fish sludge, effectively converting waste into high-quality proteins and lipids for sustainable aquafeed. Circular feeds can serve as a highly efficient and sustainable resource for perch farming by providing high-quality feed ingredients while minimising land, water, and energy use. To expand and boost perch aquaculture, the significant advantages of circular feeding must be unlocked through empirical validation, supported by regulatory frameworks and policy instruments.

3. Methodology in assessing novel circular feed ingredients

3.1. Integration of circular feed ingredients into commercial diet formulation

The test diet design is based on replacing expensive fish meal with low-cost alternative protein macro ingredients. This approach, produced through an aquaculture circularity design, features the recovery and recycling of nutrients from fish tank wastewater to generate protein biomass. The circular feed rationale focuses on reducing feed, energy, and fish production costs, as well as minimising wastewater discharge. The various protein sources generated are used to create fish feeds. These formulated feeds are enhanced with functional micronutrients. For the feeding trial, the test diets are carefully designed to assess their impact on fish growth and health using a dose-response approach. In addition, a basal diet containing only fishmeal protein is formulated and produced for comparison purposes. The diet formulations are nutritionally balanced to guarantee an iso-nitrogenous, iso-lipidic, and iso-energetic composition (i.e., all diets have the same gross nutrient values typically using a feed software to adjust for deficiency of sacrificial/compensatory ingredients, e.g., wheat flour or starch). The nutritional profile of the finished diets will be assessed for quality assurance. This involves the subsampling of the test diets for proximate and nutrient composition analysis (AOAC, 2011). To gain insights into the physiological response of farmed fish to feed circular-based generated alternative proteins, an inert trace marker (i.e., is not absorbed or digested in the gut or affects the animal's normal function). Past-tested and recommended inert markers include yttrium oxide, chromium oxide, and titanium dioxide. Although the former is preferred as it is more stable when subjected to feed production processing (e.g., high temperature and pressures) and digestion. Furthermore, given that yttrium is a rare earth metal, digestibility can be easily calculated from the collected faecal matter and the initial feed. The test feed production typically includes grinding of raw ingredients, mixing of formulated components, extrusion to form pellets, drying to remove moisture, fat coating to enhance energy content and palatability, and final cooling to stabilise the feed before packaging and storage (Figure 3).

Figure 3: A) Typical feed extrusion process and B) example of finished feed pellets used in the feed trial.

3.2. Designing fish feed trials to validate circular feed ingredients

The fish used in the trial should be commercially sourced to represent typical commercial practices (i.e., strain, diploid/triploid, or mix-sexed or all-female). Water quality (e.g., dissolved oxygen, nitrogenous waste (i.e., ammonia/ammonium, nitrite, and nitrate), temperature, and pH) should be monitored and measured daily to prevent significant variations and their impact on the fish's response to the test feeds. Fish will be acclimated for four weeks and fed a commercial diet at a maintenance ration level. Afterwards, fish will be starved for 24 hours to empty their stomachs before the start of the feeding trial, allowing them to adapt to the test diets. The fish will be randomly assigned to groups, with each group receiving a specific test diet. This allocation will follow a completely randomised block design (e.g., using a random number generator) to ensure that the effects of different diets can be accurately assessed. Additionally, each experimental group will be further randomised into triplicate tanks of 20 fish per tank. The fish is typically manually fed daily at a rate of 2-5% (depending on fish species and life stage) of the tank population biomass, or if there is a single operator during the trial, feeding to satiation could also be undertaken. However, some larger-scale feed trials (lake cage or large tank populations) use automated feeders, but this could introduce errors such as hierarchy in the fish population during the feeding periods, i.e., greater size variation due to larger being more dominant in getting the first feed preference. The feed trial is typically undertaken for approximately 8-12 weeks or until a typical threefold weight gain is achieved, which is the consensus in scientific fish feed trials (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Example of the fish feed validation trial life cycle and experimental design (L, level).

3.2. Growth and feed utilisation assessment

Growth performance and feed utilisation are considered the primary indicators in fish feed trials because they directly reflect how well a diet meets the nutritional needs of fish and how efficiently resources are being used. From a commercial perspective, growth performance and feed utilisation indices are the primary indicators in fish feed trials because they directly influence profitability and sustainability in aquaculture operations. For example, faster growth rates mean fish reach market size more quickly, allowing for shorter production cycles and higher turnover. At the same time, efficient feed utilisation is reflected by a low feed conversion ratio (FCR) and high protein efficiency. As such, reducing feed costs, which typically account for the largest share of operating expenses, is crucial to sustainable business operations. Better feed efficiency also means less nutrient waste is released into the environment, which lowers the risk of regulatory issues and supports a farm's reputation for sustainable practices. Fish are monitored throughout the trial to assess the test feed's impact by observing phenotypic features, such as head, mouth, eye, and body deformities, as well as behavioural stress, including swimming abnormalities. Bulk or individual weighing of fish in each tank is performed at the beginning and end of the feeding trial. During the trial period, fish are weighed every week or fortnight, depending on the species' tolerance to manual handling, to assess growth metrics and adjust the daily feeding ration to account for increased growth. At the conclusion of the trial, the fish population of each tank are weighed and lengths measured for the calculation of growth performance indicators, morphometric, and nutrient utilisation and digestibility indices:

Growth performance

Weight gain; $WG = \text{final weight (g fish}^{-1}) - \text{initial weight (g fish}^{-1})$

Specific growth rate; $SGR = \{[\text{Ln final mean weight (g fish}^{-1}) - \text{Ln initial mean weight (g fish}^{-1})] / \text{days fed (g)}\} \times 100$

Survivability Rate (%): $\text{No. fish survival} / \text{total no. fish (initial number of fish)} \times 100$

Morphometric

Hepatic somatic index; $HSI = [\text{liver weight (g fish}^{-1}) / \text{body weight (g fish}^{-1})] \times 100$

Viscera somatic index; HSI = [Viscera weight (g fish⁻¹) / body weight (g fish⁻¹)] x 100

Condition factor; K = [body weight (g fish⁻¹) / body length³ (cm)] x 100

Nutrient utilisation and digestibility

Feed conversion ratio; FCR = feed intake (g fish⁻¹) / weight gain (g fish⁻¹)

Protein efficiency ratio; PER = weight gain (g fish⁻¹) / protein given (g fish⁻¹)

Relative Growth Rate (RGR) (%): (Final weight (g fish⁻¹) – initial weight (g fish⁻¹)) / initial weight (g fish⁻¹) x 100

Apparent digestibility coefficient (ADC_{nutrient}) (%): $100 \times (100 - \%MD/\%MF) \times (\%NF/\%ND)$

%MD = trace marker in diet; MF = trace marker in faeces; NF = nutrient concentration in faeces (e.g., moisture, protein, lipid, energy, amino acids); ND = nutrient concentration in diet (e.g., dry matter (gross nutrient), protein, lipid, energy, amino acids).

3.3. Research ethical standards, data, and sample collection

The use of vertebrates, including fish, in scientific research studies falls within the scope of the EU Directive for the protection of animals used for scientific purposes (2010/63/EU). The goal of this legislation is to reduce the number of animals used in research, refine experimental procedures to minimise suffering, and replace animal testing with alternatives wherever possible. At the state level, implementation and oversight are administered by a designated competent authority (e.g., Ireland: Health Products Regulatory Authority (HPRA)) responsible for evaluating and approving research protocols involving live animals that include procedures (typically outside the fish feed trial scope unless they undergo procedures and challenges). Research application and oversight at the institutional level are governed by committees such as the animal welfare committee and/or the animal care and ethics research committee. These committees will assess research applications involving the use of animals and determine whether they fall within the scientific animal protection legislation, e.g., if the animals are exposed to noxious substances (e.g., bacterial challenges) or environmental conditions (extreme oxygen deprivation or temperature) beyond those typically found on the farm, or to nutrient-deficient diets. In feed formulation trials involving the substitution of one ingredient for another, provided that the nutritional requirements of the diet are still met and benign, authorisation is typically not required within the context of farm animals. Although some institutions/states might require authorisation for the collection of tissues post-mortem. Nevertheless, consultation with the research institution's animal ethics committees should be undertaken to ensure compliance with research ethics.

At the conclusion of the feed trial, typically three to five fish are randomly selected from each tank for each group of analysis, depending on the outcome expectation. Blood, fillet, liver, gastrointestinal tract, and digesta are collected for haematological, biochemical, histological, immunological, and nutrient quality assays. These fish are humanely euthanised by concussion or tricane followed by the destruction of the brain to confirm death (EU Directive 2010/63/EU). For the latter form of euthanasia, tricaine, also known as MS 222 (EC No. 212-956-8), is an approved anaesthetic agent (prescription and controlled drug) for the use in the immobilisation of fish for biosampling purposes, which includes conducting morphometrics and sampling of tissues. Upon absorption, MS-222 temporarily blocks sensory nerve conduction, which suppresses activity and reflexes while alleviating pain and discomfort. Anaesthetic dose administration is categorised by stages, which are determined by key factors including the experimental goal (anaesthesia or euthanasia), the fish species ecotype, species-specific fish size, and water temperature (Priborsky and Velisek, 2018; Carter et al., 2011; Neiffer and Stamper, 2009, Table 2). For example, the milder stages serve specific purposes: Sedation (Stage I) is applied to minimise stress during fish handling and transport, while excitation (Stage II) achieves a partial loss of equilibrium for non-invasive procedures such as tagging and minor handling. Stage III (Surgical anaesthesia) is applied for invasive procedures such as blood sampling, invasive tagging, tail biopsy, weighing, imaging, and recovery surgery. At this stage, the fish exhibits rare opercular movement, complete loss of equilibrium, and no reaction to external stimuli. Deep anaesthesia (Stage IV) is reserved for non-recovery surgery, characterised by the complete cessation of opercular movement and a total lack of muscle tone. The final stage, Euthanasia (Stage V), involves administering an anaesthetic overdose to induce death for the purpose of tissue and organ collection. Fish specimens are humanely euthanised with MS-222 at the terminal

stage of anaesthesia (Stage V) prior to tissue collection, thereby mitigating animal pain and suffering.

Table 2: Recommended/past dose administration of tricaine methanesulfonate (MS-222) (mg L^{-1}) for freshwater fish species for deep procedure (stages V).

Fish size	Salmonids	Cyprinids	Percids
Adult	60-150	80–200	50-100
Juvenile	80	50-100	100
Fingerling	20-70	20-85	50-70
Reference	Carter et al., 2011; Soivio et al. (1977); Wagner et al. (2014); Velise et al. (2011); Neiffer and Stamper (2009)	Priborsky& Velisek (2018); Witeska et al. (2017)	Jacquemond (2004); Kristian et al. (2014)

3.4. Blood sampling

Replacing ingredients typical of commercial feed-formulation diets with alternative, novel macro-ingredients can affect animal health. As primary indicators of exposure endpoints, blood markers can provide valuable information on the replacement effect of alternative protein diets on fish health. Immediately after euthanasia (approved EU methods, e.g., concussion or tricane), fish from each experimental group are sampled for blood collection. Using an appropriate gauge needle and syringe (e.g., 21 gauge with 1-3mL syringe for 40-90g fish, 5 mL), blood samples are collected via caudal puncture. Blood samples were transferred into heparinised (whole, plasma) and unheparinised (serum) tubes. Blood samples collected from the fish specimens can be used to evaluate a number of physiological, immunological, and stress parameters (Table XX).

3.4.1. Blood cell parameters

Whole blood samples from fish are collected to evaluate the haematological profile, including red blood cells, packed cell volume, haemoglobin, red cell indices (MCH, MCV, MCHC), and blood cell counts (Dacie and Lewis, 2011). This is typically analysed immediately after blood collection from the fish, while cell counts are stabilised in preservative solution for later counting, i.e., Dacie fluid. These markers are critical for assessing the primary indicators of dietary effects on haematopoietic status in fish (Table 3).

3.4.2. Biochemical parameters

Biochemical assessment of fish is central to understanding metabolic dynamics in fish nutrition, as it measures nutrient utilisation and metabolic health by analysing key nutrient levels and metabolites in fish tissues and fluids. This is crucial to understanding how the interactive effects of diet and environmental factors affect energy balance, growth, and the physiological state of the fish. Serum samples from the fish species are used to measure metabolites, including triglyceride, glucose, cholesterol, and total protein, to assess the metabolic performance in response to dietary treatments. Intracellular enzymes, alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), and alkaline phosphatase (ALP) are measured to examine the fish liver health (Sopinka et al., 2016). A dietary shift to unconventional macronutrient sources can impact fish health (Serra et al., 2024; Iheanacho et al., 2025b); therefore, the activities of key antioxidant-related enzymes: superoxide dismutase (SOD), glutathione peroxidase (GPx), catalase CAT) and lipid peroxidation are measured to evaluate oxidative stress (Sopinka et al., 2016).

3.4.3. Immune parameters

The effect of diet treatments on fish immune health is further evaluated by assessing specific immune biomarkers, including IgM, IgE, peroxidase, ACH50, protease, anti-protease and lysozyme, using commercially available ELISA assay kits. These biomarker measurements provide insight into the immunopotential of alternative protein ingredients produced through a circular feed formulation model on fish immune performance (Aragao et al., 2022). Collected blood samples (whole, plasma, & serum) from the fish specimens will be used to evaluate the fish physiological status: haematology (RBC, PCV, haemoglobin & blood cell count), biochemical (triglyceride, glucose, cholesterol, total protein), liver health (ALT, AST, and ALP etc.) and immunological (e.g., alternative complement pathway, lysozyme etc.)

Table 3: Health performance indicators to assess feed ingredient impact and functionality in the farmed fish model.

Parameter	Abb.	Unit	Indication	Method	Reference
Whole blood					
Red blood cell count	RBC	cells L ⁻¹	Gas exchange capacity, anaemia	Hemocytometry	Dacie and Lewis (2011)
White blood cell count	WBC	cells L ⁻¹	Immunological capacity	Hemocytometry	Dacie and Lewis (2011)
Packed cell volume	PCV	%	Gas exchange capacity, anaemia	Haematocrit	Dacie and Lewis (2011)
Plasma					
Glucose	GLU	mg dL ⁻¹	Metabolic energy	Colourimetry/Spectrophotometry	Sopinka et al. (2016)
Total protein	TP	g dL ⁻¹	Osmotic regulation/nutrient transport	Biuret or Bradford-spectroscopy	Barton (2002)
Aspartate aminotransferase	AST	U L ⁻¹	Liver function	Colourimetry/Spectrophotometry	Barton (2002)
Alanine aminotransferase	ALT	U L ⁻¹	Liver function	Colourimetry/Spectrophotometry	Barton (2002)
Alkaline phosphatase	ALP	U L ⁻¹	Liver function	Colourimetry/Spectrophotometry	Barton (2002)
Albumin	ALB	g dL ⁻¹	Metabolite transport	Colourimetry/Spectrophotometry	Sopinka et al. (2016)
Triglyceride	TAG	mg dL ⁻¹	Lipid function	Colourimetry/Spectrophotometry	Conlgeton and Wagner (2006)
Cholesterol	CHO	mg dL ⁻¹	Lipid function	Colourimetry/Spectrophotometry	Silva-Brito et al. (2019)
Lactate	LAC	mg dL ⁻¹	Metabolic energy	Colourimetry/Spectrophotometry	Silva-Brito et al. (2019)
Lysozyme	LYZ	U mg protein ⁻¹	Stress resistance	ELISA	Koskela et al. (2004)

Peroxidase	PER	U ml ⁻¹	Immune capacity	Colourimetry/Spectrophotometry	Quade and Roth (1997)
Alternative complement pathway	ACH50	(ACH ₅₀ ml ⁻¹)	Immune capacity	Colourimetry/Spectrophotometry	Sunyer and Tort (1995)
Protease	-	%	Immune capacity	Colourimetry/Spectrophotometry	Espírito-Santo et al. (2024)
Anti-protease	-	%	Immune capacity	Colourimetry/Spectrophotometry	Espírito-Santo et al. (2024)
Malonaldehyde	TBAR/MDA	nmol mL ⁻¹	Oxidative stress	Colourimetry/Spectrophotometry	Erdelmeier, Gerard-Monnier et al. (1998)
Immunoglobulin	IgM	g L ⁻¹	Immune capacity	ELISA	
Superoxide dismutase	SOD	μmol min ⁻¹	Oxidative stress	Colourimetry/Spectrophotometry	Sopinka et al. (2016)
Catalase	CAT	μmol min ⁻¹	Oxidative stress	Colourimetry/Spectrophotometry	Sopinka et al. (2016)
Glutathione peroxidase	GPx	μmol min ⁻¹	Oxidative stress	Colourimetry/Spectrophotometry	Sopinka et al. (2016)

3.5 Nutritional histomorphological assessment

The gut plays a principal role in maintaining fish health and the normal assimilation of nutrients, and similarly, the morphology of the liver reflects health status. The structural integrity of the fish digestive tract and liver health are assessed using conventional histology methodology. The gastrointestinal tract (e.g., hindgut) and liver are collected from harvested fish and fixed in 10 % neutral buffered formalin, processed, sectioned, and stained with haematoxylin and eosin stain (Adeoye et al., 2020). Stained samples of the liver are assessed for fatty vacuolation, hepatocyte integrity, lipid deposition, and sinusoid (Figure 5A). Similarly, intestine-stained samples are measured for villus height and width, lamina propria width, intestinal lumen diameter, and mucosal fold (Figure 5B) using ImageJ (Schneider et al., 2012).

Figure 5: A) Fish liver section showing typical histological features such as vacuolation (V), portal vein (PV), sinusoid (S), hepatocyte (H). **B)** represents the fish intestine section showing typical histological features such as lumen diameter (L), villus height (VL), villus width (VW), lamina propria width (LP), and mucosal fold (MF) (Iheanacho et al., 2025c).

3.6 Gut integrity and molecular microbiome profiling

The assessment of the gut microbiome offers valuable insights into how diets impact fish gut health by measuring gut microbial composition and structural balance. These microbes are essential for breaking down proteins into amino acids, modulating the immune system, and acting as stress markers. This information is crucial for evaluating nutrient absorption, digestion, gut immunity, and overall fish health. The gut microbial community is measured using molecular phylogenetic identification techniques. The DNA extraction is performed with commercial extraction kits (e.g., QIAamp PowerFecal DNA Kit) on the hindgut (mucosal scrapes for the autochthonous microbiome), targeting the 16S rRNA V3/V4 hypervariable region for amplification by standard PCR using Illumina metagenomic library preparation protocols. Primers used for the sequencing are readily available and used in sequencing laboratories, but bespoke primers have also been used in numerous studies in fish feed-related trials. Illumina adapters are added according to the company specifications, and amplicons are sequenced with Illumina MiSeq from both ends. The resulting joined and cleaned short DNA sequences are uploaded to the Galaxy web platform (Afgan et al., 2018) and parsed against a reference database to assign their taxonomic labels using Kraken. Taxonomic assignments are filtered, and the taxonomic codes are translated into bacterial classification using Convert Kraken. The final output is converted into a multi-level taxonomic rank file using Python (v2.7) and R (v3.5) programming and used as an input for GraPhlAn for the generation of taxonomic trees.

3.7 Gene expression

To fully characterise the effects of circularly sourced macro ingredients, research on fish must extend past nutrient utilisation and absorption to encompass the molecular regulation of relevant gene cascades. Assessment of gene expression profiles is crucial for deciphering the molecular interplay and immune responses, thereby understanding the impact of novel circular feed macroingredients on fish performance. Specifically, gene expression analysis reveals how dietary components, such as protein, lipids, or supplements, affect the activation or deactivation of specific genes (Table 4), which, in turn, influence growth, metabolism, and immune responses. Ribonucleic acid (RNA) isolated from fish tissue (liver) is extracted and purified using a recommended commercial kit. The RNA are then reverse transcribed into cDNA using the Reverse transcription master mix. The gene sequencing is conducted using the developed specific primers, which distinguish between gene variants, ensuring that at least one primer from each pair spans an exon-exon junction. Multiplex quantitative real-time PCR (qPCR) are performed on 48.48 Gene Expression biochips. Transcript levels are determined using the Biomark HD machine, following the manufacturer's thermal protocol 'GE Fast 48 × 48 PCR+Melt v2.pcl'. Raw Cq data are obtained using Fluidigm real-time PCR analysis software v3.0.2 (Standard BioTools), from which the relative expression of target genes is calculated using the δ Ct method with normalisation against the reference genes encoding elongation factor 1-alpha 1 (eef1a1), and ribosomal protein S5 (rps5).

Table 4: Examples of genes used in the assessment of feed ingredient performance and functionality in farmed fish models.

Gene	Abbreviation	Function	Reference
Inhibitor of nuclear factor kappa B	<i>IKBa</i>	Modulate inflammation and influences duration of inflammatory processes.	Liu et al. (2017)
Insulin-like growth	<i>IGF-1</i>	The expression of IGF-1 is primarily influenced by the	Saez-

factor		composition and balance of the major dietary macronutrients, specifically protein and lipid. The gene upregulation indicates growth improvement.	ateaga et al. (2022)
Insulin-like growth factor-binding protein	<i>IGFBP</i>	regulating Insulin-like Growth Factors	Saez-ateaga et al. (2022)
Fatty acid desaturase 2	<i>fads2</i>	Regulate lipid (LC-PUFA) synthesis and meat quality	Yang et al. (2025)
Nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factors	<i>nfe2l2</i> or <i>Nrf2</i>	Modulates cellular oxidative stress responses	Zhu et al. (2023)
TroponinI2	<i>tnnl2</i>	Expression levels indicate growth and muscle development resulting from dietary macronutrient changes	Saez-ateaga et al. (2022)
Mechanistic target of rapamycin	<i>mTOR</i>	Coordinates immune response prompted by dietary nutrient utilisation resulting regulation of growth, metabolism, and physiological homeostasis	Liu et al. (2025)
<i>Interleukin 18</i>	<i>il-18</i>	Mediator of inflammatory response	(Eljasik et al. 2022)
<i>Interleukin 6</i>	<i>il-6</i>	Stimulating acute phase protein synthesis	(Eljasik et al. 2022)
<i>Heat shock protein 70</i>	<i>hsp70</i>	Protein maturation, re-folding and degradation	(Eljasik et al. 2022)
<i>Heat shock protein 90</i>	<i>hsp90</i>	Protein maturation, re-folding and degradation	(Eljasik et al. 2022)
<i>Tumour necrosis factor alpha</i>	<i>tnf-α</i>	Signalling events within cells	(Eljasik et al. 2022)
<i>Mucin 5b</i>	<i>muc5b</i>	Ensure normal mucus clearance	(Eljasik et al. 2022)

3.8. Consumer product quality evaluation

Similarly, at the conclusion of the trial, fish fillets should be sampled for nutrient quality assessment. However, this would be more relevant in the context of feed trials conducted at near-harvest size. The parameters of fillet quality assessment could include fillet yield, shelf-life stability, drip loss, development of muscle colour (Konica Minolta colourimeter, Figure 6), lipid peroxidation, and sensory attributes (texture, colour, flavour, and odour by trained panel or instrumental analysis). Furthermore, the nutritional profile of the fillet or even the whole fish should also be assessed for possible changes by the change in diet, such as proximate composition (inc. moisture, protein, lipid, energy, and ash using AOAC, 2012 methodology), fatty acid composition (GC-FID), and amino acid profiles (HPLC-DAD, Egerton et al., 2020, Table 5).

Figure 6: A) Colour assessment of fillet using Konica Minolta metre, B) Schematic of the CIE $L^*a^*b^*$ colour space illustrating lightness (L^*), red–green (a^*), and blue–yellow (b^*) dimensions, C) Texture analyser used to measure fillet parameters such as shear, compression, resilience, and hardness.

Table 5: Fillet quality indicators that could be tested to assess feed ingredient impact on end-product quality

Parameter	Unit	Indication	Reference
Nutritional composition			
Moisture	% Wet weight	Higher or lower water content	AOAC (2000)
Protein	% Wet weight	Protein content of the muscle	AOAC (2000)
Lipid	% Wet weight	Leaner or fatter muscle	AOAC (2000)
Ash	% Wet weight	Total mineral and metal content	AOAC (2000)
Energy	KJ g ⁻¹	Caloric content of the fillet	AOAC (2000)
Fatty acid profile	% Wet weigh	Fatty acid, including omega-3 fatty acids, content	Sele et al. (2024)
Amino acid profile	% Wet weigh	Amino acid profile of the proteic fraction	Aas and Asgard (2017)
Mineral profile	% Wet weigh	Mineral profile, including selenium, zinc, iodine, magnesium, and potassium contents	Ytrestoyl et al. (2016)
Lipid quality indicators			

Athoreginicity index	-	Likelihood of the fat to promote artery plaque formation in the consumer	Ribeiro et al. (2017)
Thrombogenicity index	-	Likelihood of the fat to promote blood clot formation in the consumer	Ribeiro et al. (2017)
Hypo - Hypercholesterolemic fatty acid ratio	-	Ratio between fatty acids that tend to lower and increase plasma cholesterol in the consumer	Ribeiro et al. (2017)
Peroxidation index	-	Likelihood of the fat to oxidise	Ribeiro et al. (2017)
Lipid peroxidation	nmol TBA g ⁻¹	Oxidation of lipids	Ohkawa et al. (1979)
Texture			
Hardness	N	Texture indicator	Filipa-Silva et al. (2023)
Adhesiveness	J	Texture indicator	Filipa-Silva et al. (2023)
Springiness	-	Texture indicator	Filipa-Silva et al. (2023)
Cohesiveness	-	Texture indicator	Filipa-Silva et al. (2023)
Chewiness	J	Texture indicator	Filipa-Silva et al. (2023)
Resilience	-	Texture indicator	Filipa-Silva et al. (2023)
Colour			
<i>L</i> *	-	Lightness	Filipa-Silva et al. (2023)
<i>a</i> *	-	Redness	Filipa-Silva et al. (2023)
<i>b</i> *	-	Yellowness	Filipa-Silva et al. (2023)
pH and water holding capacity			
pH	-	Fillet acidity and basicity	Filipa-Silva et al. (2023)
Water holding capacity	%	Capacity to hold water	Filipa-Silva et al. (2023)

3.9. Data analysis and performance assessment

Unlike terrestrial animal feed trials, such as those for chickens and pigs, fish and shrimp feed trials are typically designed as cohort experiments in the statistical model, with the experimental unit being the tank rather than the individual animals. This approach accounts for interactions within the tank population, which can form hierarchies that affect individual growth. For example, more dominant fish get to feed first. Furthermore, it would be difficult to differentiate between individuals, and the use of tagging (e.g., subcutaneous PIT tags) for identification could add unnecessary pain and suffering to the small animals used in the initial start of the studies (note: primarily PIT tagging is used in larger harvestable fish such as marine stage salmon). Successful commercialisation of circular feed hinges on establishing the optimal inclusion levels of novel ingredients through dose-response relationship analysis. This requires a comprehensive

statistical evaluation of key growth and health parameters to accurately assess the impact of the circular-based optimised feed on fish performance, fillet quality, and sensory attributes. Initially, datasets will need to be assessed for homogeneity of variance using tests such as Cochran's C-test or Levene's test. Non-homogeneous data are subjected to transformation, such as logarithmic data conversion. Statistical tools such as Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), regression, and multivariate models are then used to evaluate the degrees of variation among the mean outcomes of the experimental groups (Shearer, 2002). The statistical comparison of treatment-group outcomes is crucial to establishing performance benchmarks that are essential to successful commercial aquaculture.

3.10. Economic optimisation

Fish feed trials are essential for both farmers and feed manufacturers to validate the performance, safety, and market potential of circular feeds and novel feed ingredients before large-scale adoption. From a commercial standpoint, these trials provide concrete data on growth performance, feed conversion efficiency, fish health, and product quality, key factors that directly affect profitability and customer confidence. For feed producers, trials confirm that new formulations using alternative or circular ingredients (e.g., invertebrate meal, algae, and fungi) can be manufactured consistently, stored safely, and deliver results equal to or better than conventional feeds. For farmers, testing ensures that these feeds support optimal growth, fish welfare, and final product quality without compromising safety or increasing operational risk. Moreover, validated feeds help both sectors meet rising consumer and regulatory demands for sustainability, traceability, and reduced environmental impact, strengthening competitiveness in domestic and export markets. In short, feed trials transform innovation into market-ready solutions by building trust, reducing risk, and demonstrating the economic and environmental value of circular aquafeeds. To assess the economic impact of using the alternatively produced mealworm as an aquafeed ingredient, the economic conversion ratio (ECR) and estimated profit index (EPI) were calculated for each experimental diet. The price of each diet (€ kg⁻¹) was calculated by multiplying each ingredient's inclusion level by its unit cost and summing the resulting values for all ingredients. Ingredient prices were obtained from publicly available databases, including FAO, IMF.org, worldbank.org and foodcom.pl

Economic conversion ratio (ECR; € kg of fish⁻¹) = Feed conversion ratio (kg diet kg of fish⁻¹) × feed price (€. kg of diet⁻¹)

Estimated profit index (EPI; € fish⁻¹) = FBW (Kg) × Wholesale price (€ kg of whole fish⁻¹) – Weight gain (kg) × ECR (€ kg of fish⁻¹)

4. Integrating environmental impact in the circular feed assessment

The transition toward sustainable aquaculture demands holistic evaluation frameworks that capture both biological performance and environmental efficiency. As novel and circular feed ingredients, such as terrestrial invertebrate meals, algae, and upcycled by-products from other food production industries (e.g., including mushrooms), enter aquafeed formulations, it becomes essential to assess their effects beyond growth and functional metrics alone. An integrative approach combining nutritional analysis, histomorphological evaluation, and life-cycle assessment (LCA) provides a comprehensive understanding of how these feeds influence fish health, organ function, and overall system sustainability. Histopathological and histomorphometric indicators reveal potential dietary effects on tissue integrity and metabolism, while LCA quantifies the environmental footprint of feed production and use. Together, these complementary perspectives enable evidence-based validation of circular feeds that support both nutritional adequacy and ecological resilience, advancing the development of next-generation sustainable aquaculture systems. To undertake an LCA for a novel or newly developed feed ingredient, the value chain needs to be established, with the system boundary, e.g., raw material production to ingredient delivery, feed produced and fed to the fish at the farm, and a resulting harvested fish product. While the functional unit, i.e., the measurable unit, should be either 1 tonne of feed ingredient or 1 kg of fish produced, to allow comparison with other studies. The primary data collection for the feed formulation is paramount, with the ingredient quantity used, energy input, country of origins and extrusion production yield, etc. The test

ingredient performance data are also critical for connecting the environmental footprint of the ingredient with its functional effects in aquaculture (Figure 7). These data can include the ingredient's inclusion rate in feed formulations, apparent digestibility of protein, lipid, and energy, amino acid digestibility (if possible), and any measured effects on feed intake, growth rate, feed conversion ratio (FCR), stress resistance, and fish health. This information allows the LCA results to be linked to overall farm-level performance and production efficiency. Impact assessment should use common categories/indices such as global warming potential, eutrophication, acidification, water use, land use and land-use change, and resource depletion. Standard LCA methods, such as ReCiPe or CML, should be applied to ensure comparability with other studies, especially those that tested circular feed ingredients. It must be noted that for each dataset, the source, year, geographic region, and technological context should be documented. The representativeness, data quality, and confidence level should be clearly stated, together with any assumptions or estimation methods used. Sensitivity and scenario analyses are recommended to test the influence of key parameters such as yield variation, energy consumption, transport distance, allocation method, and FCR or digestibility outcomes from feeding trials. Background data (missing data that cannot be obtained from the primary data, e.g., the construction of the feed ingredient production unit) can be obtained from established life-cycle inventory databases such as ecoinvent, Agrifootprint, or AgriBALYSE, while software tools such as openLCA, SimaPro, or GaBi can be used for modelling and impact calculation (Liu et al., 2024).

The integration of circular-feed usage in aquaculture requires a comprehensive cradle-to-cradle LCA to evaluate its environmental impact critically. Although circular aquaculture is aimed at increasing fish yield and enhancing product quality while improving resource management and waste reduction, its overall environmental impact must be rigorously assessed. Driven by the continuous demand for enhanced fish quality (fillet colour, texture) and increased yields, aquaculture production dynamics and strategies are evolving. However, because these strategies depend heavily on several input factors, including feed ingredients, formulation designs, and production technologies, the environmental consequences of respective choices should be critically assessed. For instance, the recent nutritional research in salmonids has focused extensively on key areas such as exploring raw materials that can legally and safely replace expensive fish meal and oil in diets without compromising fish health or productivity (Iheanacho et al., 2025; Simon et al., 2025); enhancing flesh pigmentation and quality for consumer appeal (Harith et al., 2023; Ziegler and Hilborn, 2023; Lámfalussy et al., 2025); and reducing the environmental footprint of salmonid farming operations (Budhathoki et al., 2025). Consequently, studies have utilised Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) within aquaculture systems, especially focusing on salmonids (Budhathoki et al., 2025; Henriksson et al., 2012; Bohnes et al., 2019). These investigations evaluated the environmental burdens of various farming intensities, providing critical data to guide sustainable aquaculture management. (Bohnes et al., 2019; Budhathoki et al., 2025). Comparative assessments conducted at the farm-gate level have shown that farmed salmon typically produce lower greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions compared to terrestrial animals such as beef and pork (Budhathoki et al., 2025). Specifically, salmon emissions are around 2.15 t CO₂-e per tonne, whereas pork ranges from 3.3 to 4.4 t CO₂-e per tonne, and beef emissions reach approximately 14.5 t CO₂-e per tonne (Budhathoki et al., 2025). This suggests that salmon could be considered a relatively climate-friendly source of animal protein. However, it is important to note that salmon production relies on marine-derived feed ingredients, which could result in greater use of biotic resources. Consequently, this makes salmon less resource-efficient than poultry, which has emissions as low as 1.4 t CO₂-e per tonne in certain sustainability evaluations (Ellingsen and Aanonsen, 2006). Similarly, an LCA on temperate-zone rainbow trout farming showed that fishmeal-based feed led to a higher acidification potential (AP) (fishmeal: 0.0053 kg SO₂ eq; plant protein: 0.0051 kg SO₂ eq) but a lower global warming potential (GWP) compared to plant-based (Soy, pea) protein resources (fishmeal: 1.13 kg CO₂ eq; plant protein: 1.75 kg CO₂ eq) (Wind et al., 2022). Notably, the study also reported that the GWP of trout farming (3.5 kg CO₂ eq) was lower than that of carp and tilapia farming (6 kg CO₂ eq), as well as terrestrial animals such as beef (29 kg CO₂ eq), pork (6 kg CO₂ eq) and chicken (4 kg CO₂ eq, Wind et al., 2022). In a LCA of perch aquaculture, Cooney et al. (2021) identified that feed was the major, and often dominant, contributor to the overall environmental burden, mirroring the impact profile seen in other carnivorous

finfish species. The study's LCA comparison of freshwater perch and salmon farming found that perch consistently had higher environmental impacts. Specifically, perch farming had a greater GWP (6.58 kg CO₂eq vs 5.09 kg CO₂eq for salmon), AP (0.03 kg SO₂eq vs. 0.02 kg SO₂eq for salmon), and Cumulative Energy Demand (CED) (116.97 MJ vs. 86.79 MJ for salmon). The LCA study outcomes deliver critical data for sustainable management by quantifying the potential environmental impact across various impact categories, enabling the identification of hotspots and opportunities for improved resource use, emission reduction, and waste management.

Figure 7: The inter-relationship of economic, environmental and nutritional factors that govern the decision making and use of ingredients in aquafeeds, Cooney et al., 2021.

5. Conclusion

The present report aims to illustrate the practicality and efficiency of circular feed utilisation as a strategy to optimise feed formulations for key freshwater aquaculture species, including salmon, rainbow trout, common carp, and European perch. The global discussion on aquaculture sustainability is prioritising a shift to alternative feed sources, driven by the severe environmental and socioeconomic issues stemming from reliance on conventional fishmeal. Circular aquaculture holds immense potential to advance the sector, as transitioning to sustainable feed formulation techniques, such as the circular aquafeed system, can boost growth in European aquaculture. In addition to their rich nutrient potential, circular feed resources offer significant advantages by positively influencing key metrics of fish growth and health performance. Aquaculture wastewater can be converted into a valuable bioresource for fish feed. This could be achieved by valorising fish sludge through the use of lower invertebrates, which are beneficial for the aquafeed industry. This initiative will make European aquaculture more sustainable by supporting eco-friendly aquafeed and boosting overall yields. However, the use of appropriate technology to screen biowaste materials and the implementation of strict quality control measures for end-products are essential to ensure the complete elimination of all contaminants and zoonotic risks. To fully realise the benefits of circular feed, however, robust policy and regulatory frameworks must be developed to govern system operations and provide the legal foundation for safety, market acceptance, and confidence. Successfully adopting a circular feed system requires a multi-faceted approach, including an evaluation of the aquafeed sector's preparedness for integration. Furthermore, raising awareness among stakeholders, including fish farmers, the aquafeed industry, and the public about the importance and benefits of circular feed practices is imperative for promoting sustainable aquaculture. Technical training should be provided to equip farmers with the necessary skills to embrace this transition effectively. Integrating circular feed into salmonid, percid, and cyprinid aquaculture can elevate fish yield and meat quality while simultaneously supporting responsible farming and curtailing the environmental footprint. The substantial volume of fish waste, including sludge generated by farming these fish species, can be bioprocessed into valuable feed ingredients to optimise their diets. The ability to bioprocess aquaculture

waste into high-value feed is a game-changer and represents an opportunity to reduce current feed expenses, which are a significant bottleneck in aquaculture. The transition to the circular feed model can stimulate the sustainable production of valuable invertebrates, such as worms and insects, thereby ensuring a more stable and reliable supply for aquafeed manufacturing. Nevertheless, a detailed LCA addressing the economic and environmental metrics is crucial for validating the practice's viability and sustainability. LCA provides the strategic basis for thoroughly evaluating the environmental and economic suitability of alternative feed resources, including circular feed macroingredients.

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